

PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF TUBERCULOSIS SPONDYLITIS OF THE SPINE UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF COVID-19

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The urgency of the problem. Development of the structural and functional type of degenerative and dystrophic diseases of the spine under the influence of Covid-19, here in the future tuberculous mycobacteria will cause a specific caseous necrotic inflammation. This requires the development of new modern methods for early detection and treatment of the disease, and leads to early and perfect diagnosis of patients.

Materials and methods of examination: to study the topography and morphology of degenerative and dystrophic changes in the spine, chest, and lumbar areas due to tuberculosis after Covid-19, biopsy of tuberculous spondylitis after examination in the Andijan regional phthisiatric dispensary and 30 to 65 years old in the autopsy department of the Republican SSV Center for Pathological Anatomy of the UzR we used the material obtained in the surgical practice of tuberculous spondylitis.

Research results and their discussion: The selection of the obtained materials in different age groups revealed that structural and functional changes in spine tuberculosis due to Covid-19 are age-specific and various pathological changes occur as people get older. The conclusions of the histological data obtained for examination were studied and analyzed. The results of the morphological examination show that during the first period of the process of aseptic necrosis, the soft tissues around the bones of the spine and the tissue of the periosteum are strongly swollen, the cellular and fibrous structures are shriveled and irregularly located, and vacuolated spaces appear in the interstation. Attention-grabbing morphological changes are observed in blood vessels in these tissues. It is determined that the wall of arterial vessels is thickened due to swelling and expansion due to dystrophy and disorganization of cellular and fibrous structures. Endothelial cells on the inner surface are also enlarged in size, and it is observed that they occupy a place in the cavity with a bulging appearance. On the contrary, it is found that the venous vessels are widened, the wall is thinned, plasma proteins and blood cells are concentrated inside.

Conclusion: In the patient, due to unintended medication therapy, various complications are developing in the digestive system, cardiovascular system.

The conclusions of the conducted scientific research showed that in studying the disease levels of the patients and making the correct diagnosis, it was determined that the pathomorphological changes should be determined with an individual approach to age, lifestyle and work activity.

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